

Interviews' questions

1. Please, explain how you usually design or prepare your courses (traditional design methods).
 - a. Which tools do you use? (paper notes, online tools...etc.)
 - b. Do you organize your activities based on time/schedules? (calendar, agenda...)
 - c. How much time in advance you organize your classes / courses?
 - d. Do you document the final design? How?
2. Please explain your experience about the general use of the design tool.
 - a. What are the advantages of using the tool compared to your traditional design methods?
 - b. What are the disadvantages of using the tool compared to your traditional design methods?
3. About the organization of the activities on a timeline/layers:
 - a. What do you think about the use of a timeline as a base to organize your activities?
 - (1) Which are the main challenges/difficulties of using a timeline?
 - (2) Which are the main advantages of using a timeline?
 - (3) Do you think that the timeline facilitates the planning of PBL/FC? And the design of courses in general?
 - b. What do you think about the organizing your activities based on the place where these occur (in class, out of class)?
 - (1) Which are the main challenges/difficulties of organizing the activities between in class/out of class layers?
 - (2) Which are the main advantages of organizing the activities between in class/out of class layers?
 - (3) Do you think that the two layers facilitates the planning of PBL/FC? And the design of courses in general?